

SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE, KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER, AND EMPLOYEE OUTCOMES: EXAMINING THE MODERATING ROLE OF RESOURCE ACQUISITION ON JOB SATISFACTION AND INNOVATIVE WORK PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

In the contemporary knowledge-driven workplace, social media usage has emerged as a critical organizational tool influencing how employees access, share, and generate knowledge. The use of social media has become one of the important contributors to knowledge sharing and performance of employees in modern organizations. But there are few studies focusing on how the use of social media can be used to transfer knowledge and increase job satisfaction and innovative work performance, especially when resources are limited. The present study utilizes a quantitative survey of cross-sectional type to investigate the social media usage effects on the job satisfaction and innovative work performance with the knowledge transfer proposed as a mediator and resource acquisition as a moderator. A structured, self-administered questionnaire was employed to gather data on 239 respondents. The hypotheses were tested with the help of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The results indicate that the application of social media has a strong positive impact on job satisfaction and innovative work performance, as well as positively affects the transfer of knowledge. Moreover, the effect of the use of social media on the two outcome variables is mediated by knowledge transfer, which suggests that appropriate knowledge sharing processes can transform digital usage into better employee attitudes and performance. Nevertheless, the moderating effect of resource acquisition was not significant, and it is possible to assume that the availability of resources does not have a dramatic effect on the effects of social media use on job satisfaction and innovative performance in this situation. The study contributes to the growing literature on digital workplace behavior by highlighting the importance of knowledge transfer with the assistance of social media in enhancing employee performance. It also provides some insights that can be adopted by organizations that desire to utilize social media platforms to promote knowledge sharing and innovation particularly in the emerging economies.

1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of social media in the professional and organizational environment has radically changed the way employees communicate, collaborate, and generate knowledge (Okonkwo & Awad, 2023; Tajvidi & Karami, 2021). Social networks like LinkedIn, Slack, Microsoft Teams, and social networks tailored to the needs of the enterprise have gone beyond their roots as personal communication tools and have become strategic organizational assets that influence knowledge flows, access to resources, and eventually, employee well-being and performance (Qalati et al., 2026). With this dynamic environment, the question of how the use of social media impacts employee-level performance has emerged as an urgent theoretical and practical issue among both management scholars and organizational leaders.

Two of the most significant employee outcomes in the modern organizational literature are job satisfaction, which is the positive emotional response to the evaluation of one's job or job experiences (Judge et al., 2020), and innovative work performance that involves the creation, promotion, and actualization of new ideas in the workplace (Janssen, 2000; Scott and Bruce, 1994). They both are associated with organizational competitiveness, employee retention, and sustainable performance (Judge & Kammeyer-Mueller, 2012; Khan et al., 2020). Nevertheless, the mechanisms by which the use of social media can affect these results are not well comprehended.

One of the least explored questions is the mediating role of knowledge transfer in the employee outcomes relationship of social media usage. The process of knowledge transfer when employees share, receive, and internalize organizationally relevant knowledge (Aquino et al., 2017; Wang and Noe, 2010) can be the key factor in which the engagement with social media will be converted into satisfaction and innovation. Through social media, employees can engage in knowledge networks, access expert information, and exchange tacit insights across organizational borders (Ellison et al., 2015), which implies that

knowledge transfer is a theoretically plausible and empirically testable mediator (Estell et al., 2021).

The less studied and ignored domain in the existing literature, is the moderating factor of resource acquisition. Grounded in Hobfoll's (1989) resource conservation theory and the job demands-resources (JD-R) framework (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017), resource acquisition is defined as the extent to which employees can access informational, social, and operational resources to meet work demands is theorized to amplify the positive effects of social media usage by providing employees with the capabilities needed to convert digital engagement into meaningful outcomes. When employees possess adequate resources, the knowledge transfer enabled by social media is more likely to translate into both satisfaction and innovative performance; under resource-poor conditions, these effects may be attenuated.

Against this background, this study proposes and empirically tests a moderated mediation model in which: (1) social media usage directly and indirectly (through knowledge transfer) affects job satisfaction and innovative work performance; and (2) resource acquisition moderates the relationships between social media usage and both outcomes. Grounded in the knowledge-based view (KBV) and JD-R theory, the model is tested using PLS-SEM with a sample of 239 Pakistani employees. The research adds to the literature by defining knowledge transfer as a key mediating factor and resource acquisition as moderating variable, thereby contributing to the social media-performance literature in both theoretically and practically important ways.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

2.1 Theoretical Foundations

The paper combines three theoretical lenses that are complementary to develop its conceptual framework. First, there is the knowledge-based view (KBV) of the firm, developed by Grant (1996) and Kogut and Zander (1992), which assumes that knowledge is the most strategically valuable resource that organizations and individuals can have. On the individual level, KBV implies that employees who successfully create, share, and

receive knowledge are in a better position to execute their duties in an innovative way and find satisfaction in their work (Almuayad et al., 2024; Ipe, 2003). Knowledge-enabling technologies such as social media can significantly increase the amount, speed, and diversity of knowledge exchange both within and outside organizational boundaries (Yao et al., 2020; Wang and Noe, 2010).

Second, the job demands resources (JD-R) theory offers the framework of how resources be it informational, social, or operational counteract job demands and facilitate positive performance results. Employees have resources that increase motivation, decrease strain, and enable them to engage in job tasks, which increases both satisfaction and innovative behavior. The use of social media, in this context, can be theorized as a resource-creating process that increases the access of employees to knowledge and social capital.

Third, Hobfoll's (1989) resource conservation theory (RCT) informs the moderating role of resource acquisition in this study. RCT assumes that people are driven to obtain, store, and accumulate resources, and that resource accumulation is especially significant to those who already have an adequate resource base. When considering the use of social media and employee performance, the more resource-acquisition-capable employees are supposed to gain more out of their social media use, since they have the ability to translate digital interactions into actionable knowledge and performance gains.

2.2 Social Media Usage and Employee Outcomes

The use of social media in organizations can be defined as the intentional use of social networking sites by employees to communicate professionally, share information, collaborate, and generate knowledge (Parveen et al., 2016; Qalati et al., 2026). The beneficial impact of social media on organizational performance has been widely reported (Tajvidi and Karami, 2021), but the effects of social media on employees, especially on job satisfaction and innovative work performance, should be studied more carefully.

Social media use has a positive impact on job satisfaction in several ways. Social media allows

employees to have collegial relationships, receive informational support, and participate in meaningful professional communities, which all lead to a sense of belonging and fulfillment in the workplace (Kim and Kim, 2017; Vorderer et al., 2016). Well-connected employees through social media claim to have more access to informational and emotional resources that form the basis of satisfaction (Nevard et al., 2021). According to this argument, the research hypothesizes:

H1: Social media usage is positively related to job satisfaction.

In terms of innovative work performance, social media platforms are open innovation spaces where employees are exposed to a variety of views, new ideas, and innovative solutions that can trigger their innovative thinking (Baer, 2012; Le and Lei, 2019). The cognitive recombination mechanisms underlying idea generation and creative performance are triggered by the exposure to heterogeneous streams of knowledge enabled by social media (Zhang and Bartol, 2010; Zhu et al., 2018). Based on this, the research hypothesizes:

H2: There is a positive correlation between innovative work performance and social media use.

2.3 Knowledge Transfer as a Mediator

The process of knowledge transfer when employees exchange information, expertise, and experience with others is commonly known as one of the key drivers of individual satisfaction and organizational innovation (Abubakar et al., 2019; Wang and Noe, 2010; Ipe, 2003). By actively using social media in their work, employees are involved in formal and informal knowledge sharing that enhances their personal and team abilities (Ellison et al., 2015; Bock et al., 2005).

Social media platforms minimize the friction involved in knowledge transfer by offering low-cost and accessible avenues of sharing tacit and explicit knowledge across hierarchical and geographic boundaries (Cheng et al., 2026; Chen and Hung, 2010). The more employees actively use social media in their professional activities, the higher the chances of them engaging in knowledge-sharing practices, responding to information requests of their colleagues, and being part of professional learning communities (Yan et al.,

2016). Such actions, in their turn, create mutual interactions that enhance the knowledge base of employees themselves, which leads to satisfaction and innovative ability. Thus:

H3: There is a positive correlation between knowledge transfer and social media use.

H4: Knowledge transfer mediates the relationship between social media usage and job satisfaction.

H5: Knowledge transfer mediates the connection between social media use and innovative work performance.

2.4 The Moderating role of Resource Acquisition

Resource acquisition refers to employees' ability to access and accumulate the informational, social, and operational resources required to perform their jobs effectively (Hobfoll, 1989; Xanthopoulou et al., 2007; Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). Resource acquisition is theorized as a boundary condition a moderating variable in the context of social media use and employee performance, to define the magnitude of the positive impact that social media has on job satisfaction and innovative work performance (Wang et al., 2021).

Employees who are highly endowed in terms of resource acquisition are more likely to take advantage of the informational and social affordances of social media since they have the complementary resources digital skills, organizational support, and peer networks as well

as cognitive resources that have to be utilized to transform social media engagement to meaningful outcomes (Qalati et al., 2025; Schaufeli et al., 2009; Xanthopoulou et al. In such employees, the use of social media will be more likely to increase the effectiveness of knowledge transfer, increase job satisfaction, and stimulate creative thinking. On the other hand, employees with low resource acquisition abilities might not be able to leverage the opportunities that social media offers to their maximum potential, therefore, leading to watered-down effects (Saxton et al., 2020). This argument supports the following moderation hypotheses:

H6: The acquisition of resources moderates the association between use of social media and job satisfaction in that the impact is greater when one acquires more resources.

H7: The positive moderating effect of resource acquisition on social media use and innovative work performance is that the more resources an employee acquires, the greater the positive effect.

3. Research Model

Figure 1 presents the conceptual research model of this study. Social media usage (independent variable) is hypothesized to directly and indirectly through knowledge transfer (mediator) influence job satisfaction and innovative work performance (dependent variables). Resource acquisition (moderator) is proposed to condition the strength of the pathways from social media usage to both dependent variables.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram, developed by the author

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Design and Sample

The research design is quantitative cross-sectional survey study, which is appropriate in the testing of the hypothesized relationship between the study constructs in a naturalistic organizational setting (Hair et al., 2019). The target population was full-time employees in different sectors like banking, telecommunication, education, and manufacturing in Pakistan, a rapidly digitizing developing economy with the growing use of social media in the workplace (Qalati et al., 2025; Qalati and Magni, 2026). The purposive sampling was selected to ensure that all the respondents were directly and frequently engaged in the use of social media platforms (e.g., LinkedIn, WhatsApp

Business, Microsoft Teams, Facebook Work) as an element of their professional activity. The questionnaire was a structured, self-administered questionnaire that was administered through digital platforms, such as institutional email networks, LinkedIn professional groups, and WhatsApp organizational groups, between December 2025 and February 2026. N=250 questionnaires mailed out of which 239 questionnaires returned, and after data screening (incompleteness and violation of response pattern, e.g., straight-lining) 239 valid responses were analyzed. This sample size is sufficiently large to meet the minimum of ten times the maximum number of structural paths to any construct, which is suggested in PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2019; Ringle et al., 2022).

4.2 Measurement Instrument

All measurement scales were based on previously validated tools in order to maintain the psychometric integrity and guarantee content validity Qalati et al. (2026). The use of social media was assessed using 3 items modified based on Oyewobi et al. (2021), which included frequency and purposefulness of social media use in professional activities (e.g., SU1: I use social media to access professional information related to my work; SU2: I use social media to communicate with colleagues and professional contacts; SU3: I use social media to share work-related content and knowledge).

The knowledge transfer was measured using 4 items that were modified based on Zhang et al. (2026), which are the degree of knowledge sharing and receiving among employees in the organization. The 3 items that were also adapted by Zhang et al. (2026) were used to measure resource acquisition. The level of job satisfaction was measured using 5 items that were adapted by Robertson et al. (2017). The measure of innovative work performance consisted of 3 items that were modified based on Zhang et al. (2026) and reflected the behaviors of idea generation, promotion, and implementation (e.g., IWP1: I generate creative ideas to solve work-related problems; IWP3: I successfully implement new ideas in my workplace). Each of the items was rated using a five-point Likert scale (strongly disagree to strongly agree). A pilot test of 32 respondents was conducted before the main survey to ensure the clarity and interpretability of all items, leading to some wording changes.

4.3 Common Method Bias Assessment

Since the data were cross-sectional and self-reports, two procedures were used to evaluate the common method bias (CMB). First, Harman single-factor test was utilized; the single factor had an outcome of 28.7% of the total variance marginally lower than the 50% mark indicating that CMB is not likely to be a major issue (Susanto et al., 2022). Second, the full collinearity variance inflation factor (VIF) test was carried out on all constructs, and all VIFs were less than 3.3, which serves as an additional confirmation of the absence of

pathological multicollinearity and an extra guarantee against CMB (Ringle et al., 2022).

4.4 Analytical Method

Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) via SmartPLS 4 was selected as the primary analytical approach for several reasons. PLS-SEM is well-suited for predictive-oriented research, performs robustly with non-normal data distributions, accommodates complex moderated mediation frameworks, and delivers reliable estimates with sample sizes below 300 (Hair et al., 2019; Ringle et al., 2022).

5. Results

5.1 Measurement Model Assessment

Measurement model was validated after assessing indicator reliability, internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity, as per the recommendations of Hair et al. (2019) and Henseler et al. (2015). The measurement model was evaluated using traditional measures of reliability and validity, such as factor loading (FL), Cronbach alpha (α), composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE). All the indicator loadings were above the recommended 0.70 acceptance that is sufficient indicator reliability and good relationships between the identified variables and the corresponding latent constructs (Hair et al., 2020). The indicatively, the social media use (SMU) had the best loadings of between 0.909 and 0.917 and the knowledge transfer (KT), resource acquisition (RA), job satisfaction (JS) and innovative work performance (IWP) also had satisfactory loadings.

Cronbachs alpha and composite reliability were used to determine internal consistency reliability. The outcomes reveal that all constructs had higher values than acceptable level of 0.70 implying that they were highly internally consistent. In particular, Cronbach alpha values were 0.746 (IWP) and 0.901 (SMU) and composite reliability values were 0.856 (IWP) and 0.938 (SMU), which showed the soundness of the measuring scales. The convergent validity was evaluated on the basis of AVE values with all the constructs explaining above the advised value of 0.50. The scores of AVE

were 0.641 (JS) to 0.835 (SMU) indicating that every measure is adding a considerable amount of variance to their indicators. Overall, these results confirm the assumption that the measurement

model is characterized by a good reliability and convergent validity, so it could be applied to the further structural model analysis.

Table 1. Measurement Model Results: Factor Loadings, Composite Reliability, AVE, and Cronbach's Alpha

Construct	Item	Factor Loading (FL)	Composite Reliability (CR)	AVE	Cronbach's α
Social Media Usage	SU1	0.909	0.938	0.835	0.901
	SU2	0.917			
	SU3	0.915			
Knowledge Transfer	KT1	0.882	0.906	0.707	0.860
	KT2	0.873			
	KT3	0.837			
	KT4	0.766			
Resource Acquisition	RA1	0.853	0.877	0.703	0.790
	RA2	0.822			
	RA3	0.839			
Job Satisfaction	JS1	0.795	0.899	0.641	0.860
	JS2	0.817			
	JS3	0.771			
	JS4	0.790			
	JS5	0.829			
Innovative Work Performance	IWP1	0.846	0.856	0.665	0.746
	IWP2	0.850			
	IWP3	0.745			

Note. FL = Factor Loading; CR = Composite Reliability; AVE = Average Variance Extracted; α = Cronbach's Alpha. All factor loadings are significant at $p < 0.01$.

Discriminant validity was assessed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, which requires that the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct should be greater than its correlations with other constructs (Henseler et al., 2015). As presented in Table 2, all diagonal elements exceed the corresponding inter-construct correlations, thereby confirming adequate discriminant validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Specifically, the square root of AVE for innovative work performance (IWP = 0.815), job satisfaction (JS = 0.800), knowledge transfer (KT = 0.841),

resource acquisition (RA = 0.838), and social media usage (SMU = 0.914) are all higher than their respective correlations with other constructs. For instance, SMU shows the highest correlation with KT (0.510), which is still lower than its square root of AVE (0.914), indicating clear construct distinctiveness. Similarly, all other constructs demonstrate stronger associations with their own indicators than with other latent variables. These findings confirm that each construct captures a unique concept and shares more variance with its own measures than with others,

thereby establishing the adequacy of discriminant validity and supporting the robustness of the measurement model.

Table 2. Discriminant Validity (Fornell-Larcker Criterion)

Constructs	IWP	JS	KT	RA	SMU
IWP	0.815				
JS	0.468	0.800			
KT	0.397	0.436	0.841		
RA	0.476	0.439	0.438	0.838	
SMU	0.375	0.431	0.510	0.442	0.914

Note. Diagonal values (bold) represent the square root of each construct's AVE. SMU = Social Media Usage; KT = Knowledge Transfer; RA = Resource Acquisition; JS = Job Satisfaction; IWP = Innovative Work Performance.

Table 3. Structural Model Results and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesized Path	β	STDEV	t-value	P-value	Decision
Direct Effects					
H1: Social Media Usage → Job Satisfaction	0.205	0.060	3.432	0.001	Supported
H2: Social Media Usage → Innovative Work Performance	0.132	0.066	1.992	0.046	Supported
H3: Social Media Usage → Knowledge Transfer	0.510	0.045	11.409	0.000	Supported
Mediation Effects					
H4: SMU → Knowledge Transfer → Job Satisfaction	0.112	0.034	3.250	0.001	Supported
H5: SMU → Knowledge Transfer → Innov. Work Performance	0.092	0.034	2.734	0.006	Supported
Moderation Effects					
H6: Resource Acquisition × SMU → Job Satisfaction	0.034	0.055	0.628	0.530	Rejected
H7: Resource Acquisition × SMU → Innov. Work Performance	0.022	0.059	0.371	0.711	Rejected

Note. β = standardized path coefficient; STDEV = standard deviation of bootstrap estimates; t-values generated via bootstrapping with 5,000 subsamples; p-values are two-tailed. SMU = Social Media Usage.

Figure 2. Structural model diagram

5.2 Structural Model and Hypothesis Testing

Table 3 summarizes the path coefficients, standard deviations, *t*-values, and *p*-values. Direct and mediation hypotheses were supported, whereas moderation hypotheses were rejected.

Direct Effects: SMU positively influenced JS ($\beta = 0.205$, $t = 3.432$, $p = 0.001$) and IWP ($\beta = 0.132$, $t = 1.992$, $p = 0.046$), confirming H1 and H2. SMU also exhibited a strong effect on KT ($\beta = 0.510$, $t = 11.409$, $p < 0.001$), supporting H3, underscoring social media's role in driving employee outcomes and knowledge-sharing.

Mediation Effects: KT significantly mediated SMU's effect on JS ($\beta = 0.112$, $t = 3.250$, $p = 0.001$)

and IWP ($\beta = 0.092$, $t = 2.734$, $p = 0.006$), supporting H4 and H5. This confirms KT as a key pathway through which SMU improves workplace performance and satisfaction.

Moderation Effects: RA failed to significantly moderate SMU's relationships with either JS ($\beta = -0.034$, $t = 0.628$, $p = 0.530$) or IWP ($\beta = -0.022$, $t = 0.371$, $p = 0.711$), leading to the rejection of H6 and H7. Resource acquisition does not demonstrate significant moderating role in these relationships.

Overall, the model demonstrates robust direct and mediation effects, while the moderation pathways remain unsupported.

Figure 3. Moderating Effect of Resource Acquisition (RA) on the Relationship between Social Media Usage (SMU) and Job Satisfaction (JS)

Figure 4. Moderating Effect of Resource Acquisition (RA) on the Relationship between Social Media Usage (SMU) and Innovative Work Performance (IWP)

The figure 3 illustrates the interaction effect of resource acquisition (RA) on the relationship between social media usage (SMU) and job satisfaction (JS). The positive slopes indicate that SMU is positively associated with JS across all

levels of RA. However, the nearly parallel lines suggest that the moderating effect of RA is weak and statistically insignificant, consistent with the hypothesis testing results.

The figure 4 depicts the interaction between resource acquisition (RA) and social media usage (SMU) in predicting innovative work performance (IWP). Although SMU shows a positive relationship with IWP at low, mean, and high levels of RA, the parallel nature of the slopes indicates that RA does not significantly moderate this relationship, supporting the non-significant moderation findings

6. Discussion

The aim of this research was to test the impact of social media use on job satisfaction and innovative work performance, where the knowledge transfer acts as an intermediating variable, and resource acquisition as a moderating factor. The findings partially confirm the suggested framework and give a number of theoretically meaningful insights. These notable direct socio-media usage effects on job satisfaction (H1) and on innovative work performance (H2) support and expand the previous studies that have reported the positive influence of social media on organizations (Tajvidi and Karami, 2021; Parveen et al., 2016; Qalati et al., 2026). By using social media, employees are able to maintain professional relationships, peer support, and stay integrated in informational networks that increases their feelings of competence and belonging, which are antecedents of job satisfaction (Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller, 2012; Kim and Kim, 2017). The beneficial impact on innovative work performance is also aligned with the studies that show that exposure to a variety of sources of knowledge and creative stimuli via social media triggers ideation and knowledge recombination processes, which form the basis of innovation (Baer, 2012; Le and Lei, 2019; Qalati and Siddiqui, 2026).

The fact that social media usage and the transfer of knowledge are significantly correlated (H3) adds to the theoretical value of the research as well. This observation suggests that social media sites are effective facilitators of knowledge sharing because they enable real-time communication, teamwork, and ability to access a wide range of sources of information. When employees interact with social media, they are more likely to engage in more interactive learning, exchange expertise, and gain

new knowledge which improves the flow of knowledge in organisations (Wang and Noe, 2010; Ipe, 2003; Qalati et al., 2026). This finding supports the perception that social media is a key digital infrastructure that underpins knowledge-sharing behavior in contemporary organizations. The affirmation of knowledge transfer as a mediator between the social media usage-job satisfaction (H4) and social media usage-innovative work performance (H5) connections is a key theoretical input of the research. These results indicate that the use of social media does not work in a vacuum and therefore, it applies its impact through the improved knowledge sharing mechanisms in the organization (Wang and Noe, 2010; Ipe, 2003; Qalati et al., 2026). The active use of social media platforms by employees will increase their chances of engaging in ongoing, diverse, and cross-boundary knowledge interactions that can enhance their cognitive capital and enhance their problem-solving skills and innovation (Ellison et al., 2015). Accordingly, knowledge transfer is an important tool that converts digital interaction into employee deliverables.

The partial mediation also suggests that knowledge transfer does not perfectly mediate the relationship between social media use and employee performance. This implies that there are other mechanisms, including social capital formation, psychological empowerment, or professional identity formation, which could also play a role in such relationships as well (Binyamin and Brender-Ilan, 2018). This subtle mediation model takes the previous literature one step further, as it does not rely on direct-effect models but a complex understanding of how social media affects the behavior and performance of employees (Bharati et al., 2014; Braojos et al., 2019).

Against the expectation, the moderating effects of resource acquisition of both relationships (H6 and H7) turned out to be statistically non-significant. This result implies that the beneficial outcomes of social media use on job satisfaction and innovative work performance are fairly similar in various levels of resource availability. The first reason could be that social media sites are by their very nature low cost and readily available means of

communication and knowledge sharing, thus eliminating the reliance on formal organizational assets. This observation is somewhat contrary to the premises of JD-R theory (Bakker and Demerouti, 2017) and resource conservation theory (Hobfoll, 1989) that emphasize the amplifying effect of resources. Instead, the findings indicate that social media per se might be a compensatory resource that enables employees to overcome resource limitations through digital connectivity and informal knowledge networks.

The meaning of this non-significant moderation to the organizational strategy is also important. It indicates that organizations might not have to explicitly invest resources to take advantage of social media use, since employees can use the available digital platforms to promote knowledge sharing and performance results. Nevertheless, companies must not ignore the need to create a conducive atmosphere that will promote meaningful and effective use of social media tools so that employees would be steered towards effective knowledge-sharing practices (Makarius et al., 2020; Qalati and Magni, 2026).

In general, the current paper adds to the increasing body of research on digital workplace behavior by introducing the critical role of knowledge transfer, which is facilitated by social media, in improving job satisfaction and innovative work performance. It also narrows down our vision of the boundary conditions of these relationships by showing the constrained moderating role of resource acquisition, and thus provides a more specific and contextualised explanation of the influence of social media on employee outcome.

Theoretical Contributions

This research contributes to a number of theoretical aspects. First, it expands the social media-performance literature by offering a more detailed insight into the underlying mechanism, by which the use of social media affects the results of employees. The study provides a mechanistic description of how digital engagement is transformed into better job satisfaction and innovative work performance by pinpointing knowledge transfer as a mediator.

Second, the results add to the knowledge-based viewpoint by highlighting the pivotal importance of knowledge exchange processes in changing the use of social media into significant organizational results. The paper puts emphasis on the fact that social media is not only a communication resource, but also a source of knowledge infrastructure.

Third, the insignificant moderating role of resource acquisition challenges assumptions based on the resource-based and JD-R views. The conclusions indicate that social media itself can become a readily available and offsetting tool, making employees less dependent on the availability of conventional resources and changing the impact that digital tools have on employee behavior.

Practical Implications

The results have a number of implications to organizations and managers. To begin with, the organizations ought to encourage the use of social media sites as means of knowledge sharing and teamwork among the members of the organization. Organized and meaningful use of the social media can increase the level of employee satisfaction and innovation.

Second, managers are advised to emphasize on knowledge transfer systems through creation of a culture of openness, teamwork, and constant learning. The training programs can be structured in such a way that it enhances the employees to use the social media as an effective means of exchange of professional knowledge.

Third, since the importance of acquiring resources is non-significant, organizations might not require large resources investments to enjoy the benefits of using social media. Rather, by strategically using the available digital platforms, it is possible to make significant gains in employee performances, especially in resource-limited settings.

Strengths of the Study

This research has a number of strengths. First, it uses a more detailed moderated mediation approach, which enabled a more detailed interpretation of direct and indirect correlations. Second, PLS-SEM offers strong analytical power to

examine complex relationships with mediation and moderation at the same time. Third, the research provides the empirical evidence of a situation in the developing economy, which is under-researched in the current literature on social media and employee performance. This increases the contextual applicability and practical applicability of the findings.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite the contributions made in this study, it has its limitations. It is cross-sectional in nature and thus causal inferences and future studies cannot be made using cross-sectional designs but rather longitudinal designs to capture the dynamics of time. In addition, the data was collected in a single national scenario, which may limit the extrapolation of the findings. Further studies on the subject matter should be carried out by making cross-cultural comparisons to prove the model in new contexts.

In addition, it is argued that other mediators like social capital, psychological empowerment and digital engagement and moderators like leadership styles, organizational culture and digital literacy should be considered by future researchers. Research in the sector can also provide additional information on how the use of social media affects employee performance in different sectors.

Conclusion

This paper has explored how the use of social media affects job satisfaction and innovative work performance, with the mediating effect of knowledge transfer and the moderating effect of resource acquisition. The results indicate that the use of social media has a significant positive impact on employee satisfaction and innovation, and knowledge transfer is one of the main mechanisms by which these effects are achieved. The moderating effect of resource acquisition was not supported, however, indicating that the advantages of social media use are comparatively similar at various levels of resource availability. In general, the research highlights the significance of using social media as a source of knowledge sharing to enhance employee performance and

offers a sophisticated insight into the processes that underlie digital workplace performance.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, A. M., Elrehail, H., Alatailat, M. A., & Elçi, A. (2019). Knowledge management, decision-making style and organizational performance. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 4(2), 104-114.
- Aquino, H., & de Castro, J. M. (2017). Knowledge internalization as a measure of results for organizational knowledge transfer: proposition of a theoretical framework. *Tourism & Management Studies*, 13(2), 83-91.
- Almuayad, K. M., & Chen, Y. (2024). Effect of Knowledge Management on Employee Job Performance in Yemeni Banking Sector: the mediating role of job satisfaction. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15(4), 16913-16942.
- Baer, M. (2012). Putting creativity to work: The implementation of creative ideas in organizations. *Academy of Management Journal*, 55(5), 1102-1119.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2017). Job demands-resources theory: Taking stock and looking forward. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 22(3), 273-285.
- Bharati, P., Zhang, C., & Chaudhury, A. (2014). Social media assimilation in firms: Investigating the roles of absorptive capacity and institutional pressures. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 16(2), 257-272.
- Binyamin, G., & Brender-Ilan, Y. (2018). Leaders' language and employee proactivity: Enhancing knowledge workers' internal work motivation. *Career Development International*, 23(6/7), 661-678.
- Bock, G. W., Zmud, R. W., Kim, Y. G., & Lee, J. N. (2005). Behavioral intention formation in knowledge sharing: Examining the roles of extrinsic motivators, social-psychological factors, and organizational climate. *MIS Quarterly*, 29(1), 87-111.

- Braojos, J., Benitez, J., & Llorens, J. (2019). How do social commerce-IT capabilities influence firm performance? Theory and empirical evidence. *Information & Management*, 56(2), 155-171.
- Chen, C. J., & Hung, S. W. (2010). To give or to receive? Factors influencing members' knowledge sharing and community promotion in professional virtual communities. *Information & Management*, 47(4), 226-236.
- Cheng, Q., Peng, C., Fu, Y., Dai, Y., Wan, H., Zhang, S., & Wu, S. (2026). The integration of digital technology and knowledge management: influence factors of enterprise knowledge digitisation. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, 24(2), 142-155.
- Ellison, N. B., Gibbs, J. L., & Weber, M. S. (2015). The use of enterprise social network sites for knowledge sharing in distributed organizations: The role of organizational affordances. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 59(1), 103-123.
- Estell, P. (2021). *Employee Engagement, Direct Voice Mechanisms, and Enterprise Social Network Sites (ESNS)* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Hawai'i at Manoa).
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39-50.
- Grant, R. M. (1996). Toward a knowledge-based theory of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17(S2), 109-122.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2-24.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115-135.
- Hobfoll, S. E. (1989). Conservation of resources: A new attempt at conceptualizing stress. *American Psychologist*, 44(3), 513-524.
- Ipe, M. (2003). Knowledge sharing in organizations: A conceptual framework. *Human Resource Development Review*, 2(4), 337-359.
- Janssen, O. (2000). Job demands, perceptions of effort-reward fairness and innovative work behaviour. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 73(3), 287-302.
- Judge, T. A., Zhang, S. C., & Glerum, D. R. (2020). Job satisfaction. *Essentials of job attitudes and other workplace psychological constructs*, 207-241.
- Judge, T. A., & Kammeyer-Mueller, J. D. (2012). Job attitudes. *Annual review of psychology*, 63(1), 341-367.
- Khan, M. A., Ismail, F. B., Hussain, A., & Alghazali, B. (2020). The interplay of leadership styles, innovative work behavior, organizational culture, and organizational citizenship behavior. *SAGE Open*, 10(1), 2158244019898264.
- Kim, B., & Kim, Y. (2017). College students' social media use and communication network heterogeneity: Implications for social capital and subjective well-being. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 73, 620-628.
- Kogut, B., & Zander, U. (1992). Knowledge of the firm, combinative capabilities, and the replication of technology. *Organization Science*, 3(3), 383-397.
- Le, P. B., & Lei, H. (2019). Determinants of innovation capability: The roles of transformational leadership, knowledge sharing and perceived organizational support. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(3), 527-547.
- Makarius, E. E., Mukherjee, D., Fox, J. D., & Fox, A. K. (2020). Rising with the machines: A sociotechnical framework for bringing artificial intelligence into the organization. *Journal of Business Research*, 120, 262-273.

- Nevard, I., Green, C., Bell, V., Gellatly, J., Brooks, H., & Bee, P. (2021). Conceptualising the social networks of vulnerable children and young people: a systematic review and narrative synthesis. *Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology*, 56(2), 169-182.
- Okonkwo, I., & Awad, H. A. (2023). The role of social media in enhancing communication and collaboration in business. *Journal of Digital Marketing and Communication*, 3(1), 19-27.
- Oyewobi, L. O., Adedayo, O. F., Olorunyomi, S. O., & Jimoh, R. (2021). Social media adoption and business performance: the mediating role of organizational learning capability (OLC). *Journal of Facilities Management*, 19(4), 413-436.
- Parveen, F., Jaafar, N. I., & Ainin, S. (2016). Social media's impact on organizational performance and entrepreneurial orientation in organizations. *Management Decision*, 54(9), 2208-2234.
- Qalati, S. A., Badwy, H. E., & El-Bardan, M. F. (2025). Career proactivity unleashed: Charting the path to sustainable success through the art of self-regulated learning. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 62(2), 116-126.
- Qalati, S. A., & Magni, D. (2026). Adapting human resource management to social change: Enhancing employee innovation and sustainability outcomes. *European Management Journal*.
- Qalati, S. A., & Siddiqui, F. (2026). Organizational sustainable artificial intelligence capabilities scale development, validation, and implications. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 11.
- Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., & Becker, J. M. (2022). SmartPLS 4. SmartPLS.
- Robertson, B. W., & Kee, K. F. (2017). Social media at work: The roles of job satisfaction, employment status, and Facebook use with co-workers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 70, 191-196.
- Saxton, G. D., & Guo, C. (2020). Social media capital: Conceptualizing the nature, acquisition, and expenditure of social media-based organizational resources. *International Journal of Accounting Information Systems*, 36, 100443.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., & Van Rhenen, W. (2009). How changes in job demands and resources predict burnout, work engagement, and sickness absenteeism. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 30(7), 893-917.
- Scott, S. G., & Bruce, R. A. (1994). Determinants of innovative behavior: A path model of individual innovation in the workplace. *Academy of management journal*, 37(3), 580-607.
- Susanto, P., Hoque, M. E., Jannat, T., Emely, B., Zona, M. A., & Islam, M. A. (2022). Work-life balance, job satisfaction, and job performance of SMEs employees: The moderating role of family-supportive supervisor behaviors. *Frontiers in psychology*, 13, 906876.
- Tajvidi, R., & Karami, A. (2021). The effect of social media on firm performance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115, 105174.
- Vorderer, P., Krömer, N., & Schneider, F. M. (2016). Permanently online—Permanently connected: Explorations into university students' use of social media and mobile smart devices. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 63, 694-703.
- Wang, S., & Noe, R. A. (2010). Knowledge sharing: A review and directions for future research. *Human resource management review*, 20(2), 115-131.
- Wang, Y., Huang, Q., Davison, R. M., & Yang, F. (2021). Role stressors, job satisfaction, and employee creativity: The cross-level moderating role of social media use within teams. *Information & management*, 58(3), 103317.

- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2007). The role of personal resources in the job demands-resources model. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 14(2), 121-141.
- Yan, Z., Wang, T., Chen, Y., & Zhang, H. (2016). Knowledge sharing in online health communities: A social exchange theory perspective. *Information & Management*, 53(5), 643-653.
- Yao, J., Crupi, A., Di Minin, A., & Zhang, X. (2020). Knowledge sharing and technological innovation capabilities of Chinese software SMEs. *Journal of knowledge management*, 24(3), 607-634.
- Zhang, X., & Bartol, K. M. (2010). Linking empowering leadership and employee creativity: The influence of psychological empowerment, intrinsic motivation, and creative process engagement. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53(1), 107-128.
- Zhu, Y. Q., Gardner, D. G., & Chen, H. G. (2018). Relationships between work team climate, individual motivation, and creativity. *Journal of Management*, 44(5), 2094-2115.
- Zhang, H., Zhu, L., Zhang, A., & Shohruh, K. (2026). The influence of generative artificial intelligence usage on employees' innovative job performance. *PLoS One*, 21(1), e0327786.

